

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE COMPETITION METHOD IN IMPROVING SPOKEN ENGLISH SPEECH

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ABSTRACT

Today, globalization processes are placing new demands on the education system, in particular, the development of communicative competence in teaching foreign languages has become one of the most priority areas. The formation of students' oral skills in the process of teaching English is a complex process related not only to the acquisition of linguistic knowledge, but also to the ability to freely use it in real communicative situations [Richards, 2006].

Today, globalization processes are placing new demands on the education system, in particular, the development of communicative competence in teaching foreign languages has become one of the most priority areas. The formation of students' oral skills in the process of teaching English is a complex process related not only to the acquisition of linguistic knowledge, but also to the ability to freely use it in real communicative situations [Richards, 2006].

In this regard, the competition-based learning method is recognized as an effective pedagogical approach that activates the educational process, increases motivation, and increases speech activity. The element of competition simultaneously enhances emotional and cognitive activity in students, which leads to an acceleration of the language acquisition process [Dörnyei, 2001].

The purpose of this article is to conduct an in-depth analysis of the pedagogical, psycholinguistic, and didactic effectiveness of the competition method in developing oral speech in English..

Theoretical foundations of the competition method. The competition method is based on the integration of behaviorist and constructivist approaches in education. According to Skinner's (1957) theory, positive incentives (reward system) enhance the activity of students and shape their behavior. The competition works on the basis of this mechanism - victory, points or ratings encourage the student to actively produce speech.

Furthermore, according to the theory of social interaction put forward by Vygotsky (1978), knowledge is formed in the process of communication. A competitive environment, on the other hand, involves students in competition and cooperation, enhancing communicative activity..

The method of competitions is a powerful didactic tool that directly affects the motivational state of students in the educational process. The psychological effectiveness of this method is that it simultaneously activates both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation mechanisms in students. External incentives (scores, ratings, victories, team results) encourage students to actively participate, while internal motivation arises from interest in the language learning process and the need for self-development [Dörnyei, 2001].

Dörnyei (2001) interprets motivation in language learning as a dynamic and multi-layered psychological system. According to him, the success of a learner depends not only on linguistic ability, but also on his emotional state, self-confidence and adaptation to the social environment. The competitive environment combines these components and involves the learner in an active speech process.

During the competition, students experience a number of psychological and communicative changes. First, they strive to think faster and express their thoughts more clearly, since the element of time and competition requires cognitive agility. Second, the motivation to avoid mistakes increases, which increases attention in the process of speech formation and leads to a conscious selection of language units. At the same time, the student, by comparing his speech with others, assesses his language level and realizes the need for development, which activates the process of reflexive reading.

In addition, a competitive environment significantly increases emotional activity. Students are more actively involved in the learning process due to the desire to win or contribute to their team. Emotional activity is directly related to cognitive processes, contributing to increased attention and faster processing of information.

As a result, as a result of the combined work of these psychological mechanisms, speaking anxiety in students is significantly reduced. They focus on expressing their thoughts instead of fearing mistakes, which leads to an increase in communicative confidence. Thus, the method of competitions not only increases speech activity, but also reduces the psychological barriers of students, creating an environment for free and natural communication. Competition and the process of speech production. Oral speech production is a complex psycholinguistic process that consists of several stages: thought formation, lexical selection, grammatical construction and pronunciation [Levelt, 1989]. The competition process accelerates these stages, since time constraints and elements of competition force the student to think quickly.

The method of competitions is considered a multifunctional pedagogical tool in the modern didactic system, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. This method has a comprehensive effect not only on increasing the level of knowledge of students, but also on their cognitive, communicative and social development. The integration of the competition element into the educational process activates educational activities, making it a more dynamic and goal-oriented process.

First of all, the method of competitions significantly increases the cognitive activity of students. The competitive environment accelerates the thinking process, encourages the student to quickly analyze information, compare alternative options and choose the most optimal solution. This develops not only the speed of thinking, but also its accuracy, since the student is forced to make conscious decisions under time constraints.

Secondly, this method directly contributes to the development of communicative competence. During the competition, students strive to express their thoughts clearly, logically and consistently, which improves the structure of their oral speech and communication strategies. As a result, students not only learn language units, but also acquire the skills to effectively use them in real communicative situations. The competition method also enhances the process of speech automation. The need to respond quickly, form and express thoughts in a short time develops in students the ability to use lexical and grammatical units quickly and naturally. This process increases the fluency of speech, reduces excessive stopping and searching for ideas.

In addition, competition-based activities also serve to strengthen social cooperation. Intergroup or team competitions develop students' skills in communication, exchange of ideas, strategy development, and joint achievement of results. This forms their social communicative competence and strengthens the culture of teamwork. Another important aspect is that the competition method stabilizes students' motivation. The constant competitive environment and the results achieved form the need for students to work on themselves and encourage them to develop systematically.

As Harmer (2015) noted, the introduction of game and competition elements into the educational process makes language learning a natural, interesting, and motivationally powerful activity. This increases students' intrinsic interest in the learning process and significantly improves the effectiveness of mastery..

Components of oral competence. Competition-based training develops all the main components of oral communication:

Fluency - fast and continuous speech;

Accuracy - grammatical correctness;

Pronunciation - pronunciation accuracy;

Interaction - engaging in communication;

Confidence - speech confidence.

According to Lightbown and Spada (2013), interactive activities significantly accelerate the language acquisition process.

Types of competitions and their methodological application. Various forms of the competition method are used in teaching English:

- quiz competition;
- intergroup dialogue competition;
- communicative competitions based on role-playing games;
- storytelling competitions;
- vocabulary relay.

Willis (1996) argues that task-based learning transforms language into a real communicative activity, which is compatible with competitive forms.

Practical observations. Pedagogical experiments show that students' speech activity increases significantly in lessons organized on the basis of competition. They are:

- tends to talk more;
- is less afraid of speech errors;
- learns to think quickly;

- works in a team spirit.

This process also brings about positive changes in students with low motivation.

In the process of education organized on the basis of competition, the activity of oral speech production is activated and accelerated through a number of interrelated psycholinguistic mechanisms. In such conditions, the student carries out the process of speech formation through rapid and automated cognitive operations, rather than through the usual, slow conscious analysis. As a result, the process of speech production approaches real-time and the ability to work under communicative load develops.

In the first stage, the process of semantic activation is intensified, that is, the student quickly activates in his mind the meanings appropriate to the given communicative situation. The competitive environment, due to time constraints and the element of competition, forces the student to quickly select the necessary concepts and ideas, which ensures the faster activation of semantic networks.

In the second stage, the mechanism of rapid lexical selection is activated. The student seeks to select the most appropriate lexical unit from the available vocabulary in a short time. This process increases the speed of lexical retrieval and serves to transform passive vocabulary into active vocabulary. This significantly improves the continuity and speed of speech.

In the third stage, the process of syntactic automation increases, that is, grammatical structures move to the level of automatic application rather than conscious analysis. In competitive conditions, the student is forced not to memorize grammatical rules theoretically, but to directly apply them in rapid speech production. This leads to the automation of syntactic devices.

In the fourth stage, pragmatic adaptation takes place, that is, the student shapes his speech in accordance with the communicative situation, audience, and purpose. In the process of competition, the social context and competitive environment encourage the student not only to speak correctly, but also to create an expressive and effective expression appropriate to the situation.

All of these psycholinguistic processes are fully consistent with the model of speech production developed by Levelt (1989). According to this model, speech is first formed at the conceptual level, then undergoes a stage of linguistic coding (lexical and grammatical selection), and finally is transformed into external speech through articulation. The competitive environment serves as a factor that accelerates and automates each of these stages.

In conclusion, the competition method is a highly effective pedagogical technology for improving oral speech in English. It increases students' motivation, increases their speech activity, and comprehensively develops communicative competence.

A competitive environment turns the learner into an active subject, encouraging them to use language as a real communicative tool [Dörnyei, 2001]. As a result, the language learning process becomes an interesting, interactive and productive activity..

References:

1. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior.

2. Dörnyei, Z. (2001). Motivational Strategies in the Language Classroom.
3. Harmer, J. (2015). The Practice of English Language Teaching.
4. Levelt, W. (1989). Speaking: From Intention to Articulation.
5. Lightbown, P. M., & Spada, N. (2013). How Languages are Learned.
6. Richards, J. C. (2006). Communicative Language Teaching Today.
7. Skinner, B. F. (1957). Verbal Behavior.
8. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). Mind in Society.
9. Willis, J. (1996). A Framework for Task-Based Learning.
10. Harmer, J. (2015). The Practice of English Language Teaching.

